

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF NEW METHODS IN BIOLOGY EDUCATION, INTERACTIVE LEARNING AND ITS MECHANISMS

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Abstract

The article talks about the efficiency of using technological and methodical innovations in the teaching of biology in recent years. It includes the methods and methods that are considered effective for use in biological education, new teaching principles, modern teaching technologies, etc. is attributed and efficiency is brought to attention. Also, in the article, issues of interactive training, its essence, methods and mechanisms of application in teaching biology were studied. It is also conveyed that increasing the digital and technological literacy of teachers is the need of the day. In the article, the need to convey to the public the importance of investing in the field of education as an actual issue was raised as a problem. The opportunities created by interactive training during dialog-reciprocal teaching in the educational process, the positive effect of the interactive mode, methods in a new format, and the use of digital technologies on the assimilation of biological knowledge were also explained in detail.

Keywords: biological education, interactive mode, innovative methods, digital skills

The use of new, different, research-oriented, creative and efficient methods and methods, which have begun to be used effectively in the field of education in recent years, has come to the fore. Adapting new methods and technologies to each discipline, taking into account the emerging needs, requires the integration skills of subject teachers. The use of innovations in biology teaching plays a special role in improving the teaching process and research skills. Especially in biology teaching, the use of visualization, experimentation and observation is necessary, and the use of various new methods and tools plays a special role in increasing mastery. Let's take a look at some of them:

Hands-on learning - is considered the most effective teaching method ever used. The essence of the method is that in order for students to master scientific concepts, they must not just be spectators, but also require more active participation in the teaching process. A variety of opportunities can be used to help students have a creative learning experience. For example, teaching the student how to work with a microscope instead of explaining, using VR glasses (Babayeva Z.Y., 2023) instead of talking can make the lesson more interesting and memorable. Hands-on learning is a multi-sensory approach to discovery that engages the senses and bridges connections in the brain, stimulating curiosity, interest, experience, knowledge and retention (11).

Storytelling – students love listening to stories, so explaining the topic partially by telling a story before imparting information is one of the best ways to capture the class' attention. The teacher may also explain biological facts or physical laws in the form of stories. This is mental organization and makes learning fun, as the person can remember mental stories rather than obvious facts. Some teachers present the entire concept as a

story, while others use a story to open and close the session. Some teachers just convey information on the subject. For example, we can understand the story of the Kharibulbul flower - *Ophrys caucasica*, Family Orchidaceae (12) which is an endemic plant and grows especially in Karabakh, to children. Or real events of animals can be conveyed as stories: "Rabbits live not only in Australia and Antarctica; Marmots swim well thanks to their cheeks. They use the air in their cheeks as fins; Dolphins use approximately 14,000 sounds, corresponding to the vocabulary of a person; 1,700 tastes in dogs and 9,000 tastes in humans. There are buyers; Raccoons are quite lazy, so they do not build their own nests, they use strangers' nests; Dolphins are mammals, not fish, because they feed on milk and do not lay eggs, etc." (13). Of course, technology should be used at this time, and age and grade level information should be taken into account. It depends on the ability of the teacher to attract the attention of the learners to the interesting story he will tell to clarify the topic, to develop the right teaching principle or to explain it. A variety of stories should be used to relate the topic to life. The nested loops work a bit like talking about a wise person in your friend's life, someone who taught them an important lesson. The first loops are the story of your friend and the second loops are the story of the wise man. At the center is an important lesson (14).

Role-playing games - this innovative method usually makes learning more fun, especially with students' better mastery of the lesson. As an example, we can watch a short, entertaining, logical and scientific video. For example: you can make pictures of different fruits and human organs, etc.

Social media. Different social media platforms can also be usefully used to make teaching more interesting and engaging. For example, from students on Twitter, etc. By following scientists and researchers on

social networks, sharing their new ideas in the classroom or using Feedly to improve the content of research projects, international scientific conferences from other platforms. lara, webinar, etc. participation can be ordered.

Virtual science laboratories. There are many free virtual scientific laboratories and encyclopedias available on the Internet. The use of those resources is one of the important factors for the exchange of experience in modern times. This approach gives the experience of studying the topic and conducting new researches without spending much money. Learning from current experiences, the comparative display of the results of long-term observations in an accelerated format allows for a comprehensive understanding of theoretically learned knowledge in the educational process.

Mind Maps - are an ideal way to visually represent different thought processes and help better organize science education. There are a variety of mind maps

cleverly chosen to represent a particular topic. Explaining large amounts of scientific information on a small map saves time and allows repetition and generalization. Using mind maps can also encourage the generation of new ideas and projects. Improving the interactive electronic use of mind maps reminiscent of the Clustering method in interactive learning can increase learning and interest. Programming skills must be used for this.

In the peer teaching method, students encourage the excitement of learning science and take on the role of teaching each other. Currently, in Peer-to-Peer learning, they actually work in teams to discuss scientific topics, ask questions, and discover new knowledge.

Fishbone - is a different, interesting, effective approach to solving problems in science and a visual tool for organizing critical thinking. Fishbone diagram - helps teach students the root causes of problems and measures the relationship between cause and effect. (Diagram 1.)

Diagram 1.
Fishbone diagram

It is more effective to use this scheme when teaching a group. In this diagrammatic approach, the head of the fish represents the change, the ribs indicate the reason, and the stripes record the supporting evidence (Diagram 2.).

Diagram 2.
Fishbone diagram

There are different approaches to the fishbone diagram, a visual tool used to identify the root causes of a problem. This method is a more structured approach. The problem or effect is indicated on the head of the fish and possible causes are listed under different categories along the small bones of the fish. It is also possible to create nested causes in the diagram. (Watson, Gregory H. et al., 2019; 8).

Or the following method can be **applied**: In the background of the music, the teacher's explanation: Life has developed by itself. Finally, there is a creature that stands before birth: Homosapiens. This is a conscious person. He did not want to depend on nature, on the contrary, he wanted to consume all the resources of nature. He cut down the centuries-old forests, polluted

the clean water sources, and dried up the rivers. Interview with students: What does "ecological crisis" mean? - What are the reasons? - Can these be prevented? What ways can you suggest to get rid of the ecological crisis?

Then, the process continues with the announcement of the subject's name, purpose and main questions of the lesson. The class is divided into "expert" groups and each group gets its own task: let's look at the results of the group called "experts": meteorologists, hydrobiologists, agricultural experts, biologists, doctors, lawyers:

Meteorologists: Man has burned large quantities of coal, oil and gas, operated nuclear power plants and increased the temperature of the atmosphere. As a result, the amount of carbon dioxide in the air increases. Carbon dioxide creates a greenhouse effect. That is, by sending the sun's rays to the earth's surface, it allows the heat to go into space. Products that destroy the ozone layer fall into the atmosphere, clouds of harmful gases are formed in the air, as a result of the operation of the thermal power plants of the cars, sulfur and nitrogen gas enter the atmosphere, combine with water and turn into nitric acid, and sulfuric acids fall to the earth in the form of acid rain. So an environmental crisis is emerging.

Hydrobiologists: The hydrosphere is the earth's water layer. Water is the basic substance of life. Matter and heat exchange occurs with the help of water. The world's ocean waters are the main factor that creates the climate and habitat for many living things. It is the main natural source of human food products. The main ways of water pollution:

1) *Physical - Increase in the amount of sand and clay in the water (as a result of soil washing).*

2) *Chemical – mixing various harmful, disease-causing organic and inorganic substances into water.*

After this explanation, the study is terminated. Students' performance is evaluated.

Why **science clubs** - are an ideal approach to STEAM education that involves high-level hands-on learning in schools or the community:

- *sharing new events in the world of science for science lovers;*

- *It is the most appropriate place to discuss innovative ideas and compare them with what they have learned.*

In general, the modern teaching methodology of biology creates the need for a different approach in teaching, as it requires a wider range of creativity and research than other subjects. The modern age has provided countless opportunities for this, as well as various opportunities for the easy use of world experience and the exchange of experiences. These include: internet resources, social networks, emails, programs that enable activities in various online formats, technological capabilities, digital skills, etc.

Recently, interactive teaching and its various methods have been used in the study of biology. During this course process, which is carried out in an interactive regime, collegiality plays a special role in the relations between the teacher and the student. For this reason, it is the main duty of teachers to pay attention to the use of modern teaching methods and principles in biology courses, which must be taught in an interactive format. In fact, the ones we mostly use in the study of biology are the cluster, Blum taxonomy, insert, BÍBO table, Venn diagram, etc. The methods are conducive to a comprehensive understanding of the subject (Babayeva Z.Y., 2023; 15). For this, it is necessary to understand the mechanism of using new techniques and tools correctly.

Mechanisms of interactive teaching include:

- Creating an interactive lesson, determining its stages, researching the goals and results of each stage;
- To take into account the stages of the revision process related to the creation of an active lesson, to ensure that the traditional lesson is explanatory-explanatory;
- Analyzing whether the application method in the active lesson is more creative;
- Acquaintance with the reflex, which is a different stage of the active lesson.

The correct progress of the stages of the interactive lesson also makes the teaching process more dynamic and interesting. Creating motivation is one of the main problems. Motivation is the introduction of a problem prepared at the beginning of the lesson to draw the attention of the class to a new topic. Or creating a problem situation with various questions and suggestions is thought to be useful in terms of motivation (Babayeva, Z. 2021). This is implemented in various ways. In addition, the BÍBO table is one of the interesting organizations used in the organization of interactive courses.

Table 1.

BIBO table structure		
<i>We know</i>	<i>We want to know</i>	<i>We learned</i>

The principles of interactive training: where the teacher will start each lesson, what stage will be followed, what the participants will be doing in the group, the tasks to be performed after the group work, what they will be doing after the discussion, what stage the lesson will end with and should consider what each phase of the interactive lesson will result in. The answers to these questions are reflected in the table below:

Table 2.

The stages of the interactive lesson and the results

Stages of the interactive lesson	Conclusion
1. Motivation (problem setting, hypotheses)	Research question and hypotheses
2. Conducting research (searching for facts to test hypotheses)	Research works
3. Information exchange (presentation of obtained information)	Information sources = discussion material
4. Discussion and organization of information (discussion, classification, coordination of information)	Organized information
5. Drawing conclusions (comparing the results with the hypotheses and drawing a conclusion about whether they are confirmed or not)	Acquired knowledge (generalization)
6. Productive (creative) application	Ways and experience of applying knowledge
7. Evaluation or Reflection (can be done at any stage)	Self-evaluation, mastering the rules of learning, the habit of independent study

In order to use modern teaching, teaching methods, methods and tools, new teaching technologies on the spot and correctly, subject teachers themselves must have digital skills and be able to use world experience in their work. The New World Order requires fundamental reforms in the field of education as well as in all areas of life. Educators are obliged to take advantage of the current innovations in order to train creative, productive, researching youth with different imaginations, which are the principles of the STEAM method (10; 15). Significant investments of the public and state structures in this field is one of the urgent problems. Early investments in the STEAM method are paying off all over the world. (Babayeva Z.Y. 2023) Thanks to this foresight, products produced with low financial costs play an important role in reducing costs. It is also necessary to add the use of recycled materials. Of course, the education system cannot keep up with the pace of rapidly developing technologies. However, in order to learn new technologies and use them as new learning technologies, care should be taken to develop teachers' technological literacy.

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